

SHAPE-MEMORY POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES WITH A 3D CONDUCTIVE NETWORK FOR BIDIRECTIONAL ACTUATION

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EXTRAND ABSTRACT

Electrical stimulation has many advantages than thermal methods for shape-memory polymers (SMPs); the bulk polymers is essential for developing high performance electroactive systems and creating an efficient conductive path¹⁻³. Here, we show that a three-dimensional (3D) porous carbon nanotube sponge can serve as a built-in integral conductive network to provide internal, homogeneous, in situ Joule heating for shape-memory polymers, thus significantly improving the mechanical and thermal behavior of SMPs. As a result, the 3D nanocomposites show a fast response and produce large exerting forces during shape recovery. We further studied the construction of a double-layer composite structure for bidirectional actuation, in which the shape change is dominated by the temperature-dependent exerting force from the top and bottom layer. Our large stroke shape-memory nanocomposites have promising applications in many areas including artificial muscles and bionic robots⁴⁻⁵.

FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1. TEM image of the CNTs exposed uniformly from the fractured section

Figure 2. Nitrogen adsorption image of the CNTs

Figure 3. SEM image of the composites fractured section at different magnification

Figure 4. Composite materials under the 17 V voltage response process

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